

A NEW CONSTANT LIFE DIAGRAM MODEL FOR UD LONGITUDINAL FATIGUE

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ABSTRACT

A new constant life diagram (CLD) model featuring asymmetric bilinear constant-life curves was proposed to better describe the longitudinal fatigue behavior of unidirectional laminae (UD) under a wide range of stress ratios. This model is able to predict S-N curves with satisfactory accuracy not only in tension-tension (T-T) fatigue mode, but also in tension-compression (T-C) and compression-compression (C-C) modes, whereas the conventional Goodman CLD model shows inferior performance especially in T-C and C-C modes. Besides static tension and compression tests, high- and low-cycle fatigue tests at two stress ratios corresponding to T-T and C-C modes should be performed respectively to determine parameters in the proposed model. Fatigue test data of several different GFRP UD's at various stress ratios were utilized to validate the proposed model in this study, and S-N curves predicted by the proposed model agreed well with experimental results. Comparing with Goodman CLD model, the proposed CLD model provides enhanced predictive capability without losing simplicity.

1 INTRODUCTION

As the application of continuous fiber reinforced composites is increasingly extensive in major load-bearing components in large structures, such as fuselage and wing box of intercontinental airliners, blades of mega-watt wind turbines, risers in deepwater oil platforms, durability of composites against fatigue loading is drawing more and more attention from both industries and academia. Since the longitudinal direction of unidirectional laminae (UD) is the main load-carrying direction, understanding longitudinal fatigue behavior is the most critical step towards establishing a fatigue life prediction methodology universally applicable to multi-directional laminates and other composites with various fiber architectures. Furthermore, UD longitudinal response under tension-compression (T-C) and compression-compression (C-C) fatigue should be treated as important as that under tension-tension (T-T) fatigue, because T-C and C-C loadings are no less common than T-T in reality: for instance, in a wind turbine blade during normal operation, the spar cap on the pressure side is mainly subject to T-T fatigue, while the one on the suction side is under C-C fatigue, as illustrated in Figure 1.

The constant life diagram (CLD) is a straightforward yet comprehensive description of the correlation between mean stress σ_{mean} , stress amplitude σ_{amp} , and number of cycles to failure N_f under uniaxial constant amplitude loading. First introduced in late 19th century [1], the CLD is still widely used in fatigue life assessment of not only metals but also composites, in spite of its phenomenological nature. Currently, the Goodman CLD model and its variants are most popular, and have been accepted by major certification agencies such as Germanischer Lloyd (GL) and Det Norske Veritas (DNV) as the approach for fatigue life evaluation of FRP in wind turbines [2], [3]. Nevertheless, arguments on the poor accuracy of Goodman model for composites are widespread among researchers. Harris et al. [4][7] proposed bell-shaped constant-life curves determined by a formula with three parameters, which are functions of σ_{mean} . Kawai and Koizumi [8] developed an anisomorphic CLD model for composite

laminates, which can be constructed using laminate static tensile strength $T(>0)$ and compressive strength $C(>0)$, together with the S-N curve obtained at the critical stress ratio $\chi \equiv -C/T$. Each constant-life curve is composed of two smooth segments connected at the point corresponding to χ . Later Kawai and Murata [9] modified the formulation by inserting a transitional segment in the constant-life curve between χ and the newly defined sub-critical stress ratio χ_s , to improve the accuracy of prediction for angle-ply ($[\pm 30]_{3S}$, $[\pm 45]_{3S}$, $[\pm 60]_{3S}$) carbon/epoxy laminates. Recently Kawai et al. [10][11] also introduced temperature dependence in the CLD formulation, and demonstrated the effectiveness in predicting fatigue life of woven carbon fabric/epoxy laminate at multiple temperature levels. Instead of fitting fatigue test data, Kassapoglou [12][13] derived and validated a CLD formulation which is based on the assumption of constant cycle-by-cycle failure probability under constant amplitude loading. Vassilopoulos and colleagues compared the predictive capability of several existing CLD formulations [14], and suggested a piecewise non-linear CLD model through interpretation of fatigue data plotted on $R - \sigma_{amp}$ plane [15]. Due to the lack of satisfactory models, numerous time-consuming fatigue tests had to be conducted to acquire enough data to construct CLDs for a variety of multi-directional laminates [16].

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of fatigue loadings applied to spar caps in a wind turbine blade during operation: T-T on the pressure side, C-C on the suction side.

Rather than being overwhelmed by the complexity of CLDs for multi-directional laminates, we revisited UD longitudinal test data under T-T and C-C constant amplitude loadings. A common observation was that S-N curves fitted using C-C fatigue test data appear flatter than those fitted using T-T test data; for GFRP UD especially, T-T and C-C S-N curves (typically with stress ratios $R = 0.1$ and 10) usually intersect with each other when plotted together on $\sigma_{amp} - \log N_f$ plane, where σ_{amp} is the stress amplitude. Little information about such a phenomenon can be found in literature, including all aforementioned models, and Goodman model is obviously unable to describe it. The difference exhibited by S-N curves reflects intrinsic UD longitudinal response to T-T and C-C fatigue loadings, and cannot be overlooked. Therefore, we hereby propose a new CLD model, aiming to provide more accurate description of the overall UD longitudinal fatigue behavior, particularly under T-T and C-C modes.

2 THE NEW CLD MODEL

2.1 Model development

Figure 2 shows typical T-T and C-C S-N curves for GFRP UD. It can be seen that such behavior is quite understandable: conceptually materials tend to show stronger resistance against fatigue loading in C-C mode than in T-T mode, because propagation of cracks is suppressed in C-C mode while promoted in T-T mode; however, the microstructure of UD features unidirectional thin fibers embedded in relatively soft polymeric matrix, and it easily loses stability under high C-C fatigue load in longitudinal direction, leading to structural failure in micro-scale prior to material failure.

Figure 2: Typical S-N curves of GFRP UD under T-T and C-C fatigue loadings.

On the other hand, typical Goodman CLD for UD longitudinal fatigue [2] features isosceles triangular constant-life curves, anchored to the horizontal axis at X and $-X'$, as shown on the left-hand-side of Figure 3. Goodman model requires one experimentally obtained S-N curve (usually in T-T mode) to determine evolution of constant-life curves versus N_f ; nevertheless, as explained in the preceding paragraphs, different failure mechanisms are involved in T-T and C-C fatigue, and consequently the information carried by one S-N curve is inadequate to well characterize UD fatigue behavior in a wide range of stress ratios. Naturally, T-T and C-C S-N curves generated from Goodman CLD will never show the phenomenon of crossing-over, as illustrated on the right-hand-side of Figure 3.

Figure 3: Typical Goodman CLD for UD longitudinal fatigue and resulted T-T and C-C S-N curves.

The target of the new CLD model is being able to describe UD longitudinal fatigue behavior under T-T, T-C, and C-C modes with higher accuracy, and meanwhile retaining the simplicity of Goodman model. Therefore, the new CLD model is supposed to bear the following features:

(1) The constant-life curves in the proposed CLD are still bilinear, with UD longitudinal tensile strength $X(>0)$ and compressive strength $-X'(<0)$ serving as two anchor points on the horizontal axis, which is the same as Goodman model.

(2) Bilinear constant-life curves can be asymmetric and bias leftward gradually as N_f increases, resulting in relatively sparse distribution of the right-hand-side segments of constant-life curves and relatively dense distribution of their left-hand-side counterparts.

(3) Two experimentally determined S-N curves, one in T-T mode, the other in C-C mode, are required to define the dependency of the shape of constant-life curves on N_f .

2.2 Formulation of the new CLD model

Based on those three foregoing features, the newly proposed CLD model (named as HH model) for UD longitudinal fatigue was formulated as below:

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_{\text{eff}} = \frac{\sigma_{\text{amp}} T}{\beta \sigma_{\text{mean}} + \frac{(T+C) - \beta(T-C)}{2} - \left| \sigma_{\text{mean}} - \frac{(T-C) - \beta(T+C)}{2} \right|} \\ \sigma_{\text{eff}} = b N_f^{-\frac{1}{n}} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where σ_{eff} is the stress-ratio-independent effective stress corresponding to the given number of cycles to failure N_f ; β controls the deviation of the peak of constant-life curve from the centerline between X and $-X'$, and β is assumed as a linear function of N_f in log-scale

$$\beta = \frac{1}{\mu} \log N_f + \beta_0 \quad (2)$$

Parameters b , n , μ , and β_0 are constants to be determined from experimentally obtained T-T and C-C S-N curves.

The geometric characteristics of the new CLD are illustrated in Figure 4: the peak of the constant-life curve deviates horizontally by $|\beta|(X+X')/2$ from the centerline between two anchor points, which also serves as the axis of symmetry of Goodman CLD. If substituting $\sigma_{\text{mean}} = [(X-X') - \beta(X+X')]/2$ into Eq.(1), the vertical coordinate of the peak is calculated as

$$\sigma_{\text{amp}} = (1 - \beta^2) \frac{X+X'}{2X} \sigma_{\text{eff}} \quad (3)$$

Depending on the sign of the horizontal coordinate of the peak, the intercept of the constant-life curve on the vertical axis can be calculated by substituting $\sigma_{\text{mean}} = 0$ into Eq.(1)

$$\sigma_{\text{amp}} = \begin{cases} (1 + \beta) \frac{X'}{X} \sigma_{\text{eff}} & \sigma_{\text{mean}} \geq \frac{(X-X') - \beta(X+X')}{2} \\ (1 - \beta) \sigma_{\text{eff}} & \sigma_{\text{mean}} < \frac{(X-X') - \beta(X+X')}{2} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

If denoting the slopes of the right-hand-side and left-hand-side segments of the bilinear constant-life curve as s_1 and s_2 , respectively, the horizontal coordinate of the peak can be re-expressed in terms of those slopes as

$$\sigma_{\text{mean}} = \frac{s_1 X + s_2 X'}{s_1 - s_2} \quad (5)$$

Equating the right-hand-side of Eq.(5) to $[(X - X') - \beta(X + X')]/2$, which is the horizontal coordinate of the peak, β can be related to those slopes as

$$\beta = \frac{s_2 + s_1}{s_2 - s_1} \quad (6)$$

Likewise, the vertical coordinate of the peak can be expressed in terms of s_1 and s_2 as

$$\sigma_{\text{amp}} = \frac{s_1 s_2}{s_1 - s_2} (X + X') \quad (7)$$

Equating right-hand-sides of Eq.(7) and Eq.(3), and using Eq.(6), σ_{eff} can also be related to those slopes as

$$\sigma_{\text{eff}} = \frac{s_2 - s_1}{2} X \quad (8)$$

Eq.(6) and Eq.(8) are especially useful in determining parameters b , n , μ , and β_0 .

Figure 4: Geometric characteristics of HH CLD.

2.3 Procedures of parameter determination

To determine parameters b , n , μ , and β_0 in Eq.(1) and Eq.(2), the procedures below should be followed:

(a) Perform UD longitudinal fatigue tests at a minimum of two load levels, one in low-cycle region and the other in high-cycle region, in both T-T and C-C modes. At least three test data should be generated at each load level to ensure statistical consistency. Load levels and stress ratios should be adjusted according to need.

(b) Fit test data using Eq.(9) to obtain analytical expressions of T-T and C-C S-N curves.

$$\sigma_{\text{amp}} = c N_f^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (9)$$

(c) Select one fatigue life in low-cycle region (denoted as $N_{f,1}$) and one in high-cycle region (denoted as $N_{f,2}$); denote points corresponding to $N_{f,1}$ on T-T and C-C S-N curves as points 1, 2, points corresponding to $N_{f,2}$ as points 3, 4, respectively; mark points 1, 2, 3, 4 on $\sigma_{\text{mean}} - \sigma_{\text{amp}}$ plane.

(d) Connect the anchor point X located on the positive horizontal axis and point 1, as well as the other anchor point $-X'$ located on the negative horizontal axis and point 2, using straight lines. Extend those two lines until they intersect, and a bilinear constant-life curve corresponding to $N_{f,1}$ is constructed.

(e) Denote slopes of line segments passing through points 1 and 2 as s_1 and s_2 , respectively. The slope of each segment can be simply calculated using the formulae below

$$\begin{cases} s_1 = \frac{\sigma_{\text{amp}}^{(1)}}{\sigma_{\text{mean}}^{(1)} - X} & R \in (0,1) \\ s_2 = \frac{\sigma_{\text{amp}}^{(2)}}{\sigma_{\text{mean}}^{(2)} + X'} & R \in (1,+\infty) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where $\sigma_{\text{mean}}^{(i)}$ and $\sigma_{\text{amp}}^{(i)}$ are coordinates of point i .

(f) Calculate β_1 and $\sigma_{\text{eff},1}$ corresponding to $N_{f,1}$ using Eq.(6) and Eq.(8), respectively.

(g) Repeat steps (d) to (f) to construct the constant-life curve corresponding to $N_{f,2}$, and calculate β_2 , $\sigma_{\text{eff},2}$ accordingly.

(h) Determine b , n using $\sigma_{\text{eff},1}$, $\sigma_{\text{eff},2}$, and Eq.(1); determine μ , β_0 using β_1 , β_2 , and Eq.(2).

All procedures explained above are shown schematically in Figure 5. With parameters b , n , μ , and β_0 determined, constant-life curves corresponding to any N_f can be easily composed. As a result, the S-N curve for any stress ratio can be determined graphically: first draw a radial line from the origin of $\sigma_{\text{mean}} - \sigma_{\text{amp}}$ plane, representing the stress ratio in need; then re-plot all intersecting points between the radial line and constant-life curves on conventional $\sigma_{\text{amp}} - \log N_f$ plane; finally connect those points on $\sigma_{\text{amp}} - \log N_f$ plane using smooth curve, and the construction of one S-N curve is complete.

Figure 5: Schematic explanation of procedures to determine parameters in HH CLD model.

3 MODEL VERIFICATION

To demonstrate the advantage of HH model over conventional Goodman model in describing T-C and C-C fatigue behavior of UD, two UD materials were utilized: one is glass/epoxy from our industrial partner, denoted as UD-1; the other is glass/polyester in Ref. [17], designated as UNI-(0)2-UP2. The matrix used in UD-1 is the epoxy resin system constituted by EPIKOTETM Resin MGS[®] RIMR135 and

EPIKURE™ Curing Agent MGS® RIMR 137 from Momentive Special Chemicals Inc., mixed in a ratio of 100:30 by weight; the fiber however is proprietary and the product name is kept undisclosed. The fiber volume fraction of UD-1 is 0.56. The other material UNI-(0)2-UP2 has the same constituents as UNI-D155B-UP2, but with a higher fiber volume fraction ($V_f = 0.5$). Longitudinal fatigue test data for both materials were available at $R = 0.1, 10, \& -1$, among which T-T ($R = 0.1$) and C-C ($R = 10$) data were fitted using Eq.(9) For UD-1, fitted parameters c, m in Eq.(9) are 583.90 MPa, 11.90 for $R = 1$, and 443.84 MPa, 27.38 for $R = 10$, respectively; for UNI-(0)2-UP2, those two parameters are 635.82 MPa, 11.05 for $R = 0.1$, and 274.99 MPa, 20.72 for $R = 10$, respectively. For both materials, $N_{f,1}$ and $N_{f,2}$ were chosen as 103 and 108 cycles, which gives parameters in HH model as $b = 1060.47$ MPa, $n = 13.31$, $\mu = 19.26$, $\beta_0 = 0.0337$ for UD-1, and $b = 1083.32$ MPa, $n = 12.23$, $\mu = 24.39$, $\beta_0 = 0.1107$ for UNI-(0)2-UP2. On the other hand, the slope parameter m in Goodman model was determined from T-T fatigue test data as 9.06 and 9.18 for UD-1 and UNI-(0)2-UP2, respectively.

Figure 6: Comparison between test data and (a) CLD based on HH model, (b) CLD base on Goodman model, (c) S-N curves predicted by both HH and Goodman models, for UD-1.

CLDs for UD-1 based on HH model and Goodman model are presented in Figure 6(a) and Figure 6(b). Stresses corresponding to different N_f values for $R = 0.1, 10, \text{ and } -1$ were back-calculated from S-N curves fitted using fatigue test data, and superposed onto all CLDs to provide straightforward assessment of accuracy. It can be clearly observed that in Fig. 6(a), test data at $R = 0.1$ and 10 are quite close to their corresponding constant-life curves, except that for $R = 10$ the stresses in the high-cycle region ($N_f \geq 10^7$) predicted by the CLD are lower than test data. Noticeably, test data of $R = -1$, i.e. along the vertical axis, are also described by HH CLD satisfactorily, except minor underestimation in the high-cycle region. The Goodman CLD however, greatly underestimates the T-C test data at $R = -1$, and the situation worsens when comparing with test data at $R = 10$, as observed in Figure 8(b). Although the Goodman CLD still matches T-T test data in relatively high accuracy, its overall performance is inferior to HH model. Figure 8(c) shows comparison between test data of $R = 0.1, 10, -1$ and S-N curve for those stress ratios predicted by both HH and Goodman models. S-N curves predicted by HH model passes through most of their corresponding data points, while only S-N curve for $R = 0.1$ predicted by Goodman model well agrees with test data, and S-N curves for the other two stress ratios predicted by Goodman model deviate far away from test data.

Figure 7: Comparison between test data and (a) CLD based on HH model, (b) CLD base on Goodman model, (c) S-N curves predicted by both HH and Goodman models, for UNI-(0)2-UP2.

Figure 7(a) and Figure 7(b) show CLDs based on HH model and Goodman model for UNI-(0)2-UP2, together with test data at $R = 0.1, 10, -1$. HH CLD well predicts both T-T and C-C test data, while slightly underestimates T-C test data. Goodman CLD overestimates test data at $R = 0.1$ in the low-cycle region and underestimates test data in the high-cycle region; for $R = 10$ and -1 , test data are mostly underestimated by Goodman CLD. It can be seen more clearly in Figure 7(c) that test data at $R = 0.1$ and 10 are well described by S-N curves predicted by HH model for corresponding stress ratios, while the S-N curve for $R = 0.1$ predicted by Goodman model well matches test data, but the agreement for $R = 10$ is poor. Note that a turning point appears near $\log N_f = 4.5$ on the S-N curve of $R = 0.1$ predicted by Goodman model, which is due to the vertically aligned peaks of constant-life curves from Goodman model and unavoidable. For $R = -1$ S-N curve from HH model apparently outperforms its counterpart from Goodman model. Again, the comparison between the predictive capability of HH model and that of Goodman model shows that due to insufficient information included in Goodman model, its accuracy in a wide range of stress ratios cannot be guaranteed, while the performance of HH CLD model is quite stable, and insensitive to material type.

4 CONCLUSION

A newly proposed CLD model (named as HH model) for UD longitudinal fatigue was introduced in this work. The model is intended to offer better prediction of UD longitudinal behavior under T-T, T-C, and C-C fatigue modes. Therefore, two S-N curves at T-T and C-C fatigue modes are required to define parameters in HH model while each S-N curve should be fitted using fatigue test data obtained at minimum of two different load levels. A systematic procedure for CLD construction and parameter determination was given.

UD longitudinal fatigue test data for glass/epoxy and glass/polyester at $R = 0.1, 10, -1$ were utilized to further evaluate the performance of HH CLD model. It turned out that HH model is not only able to predict test data at $R = 0.1$ & 10 , but also able to offer satisfactory predictions at $R = -1$. Finally, it was also noticed that test at $R = -1$ in high-cycle region were often slightly underestimated by HH model, which suggests that further improvements may be carried out in the future to better describe UD longitudinal T-C fatigue.

In summary, the HH CLD model proposed in this work is a simple yet effective tool for life prediction of UD under longitudinal fatigue. Comparing with conventional Goodman model, a few more efforts are needed by HH model for material characterization, but it is able to describe UD longitudinal fatigue behavior under T-T, T-C, and C-C loading modes with satisfactory accuracy. In addition, although the HH model is initially proposed for UD longitudinal fatigue, the concept and procedures can be actually applied to any materials exhibiting different fatigue behavior under T-T and C-C fatigue. Finally, the CLD model proposed in this work has been proven effective but is still phenomenological, and more solid physical explanations will be provided by the incoming work.

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